

Graphite based carbon nanostructures

- With focus on its usefulness in the industry and in the production of solar cells

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ABSTRACT

This report is about two of carbons allotropes, graphite and graphene. It will be about some of its special properties and characteristics. Because of this, it will necessarily be a study of these two interesting materials on a nanometer scale. Carbon has several other allotropes including diamonds, fullerenes and carbon nanotubes. Allotropes are different structural forms of the same element and can have quite different physical and chemical behaviors. Fullerenes and carbon nanotubes are also interesting when looking at it from a nanotechnology point of view but these are not focused upon in this report. It touches upon the use, the problems and the exciting potential it contains. It was concluded that these carbon nanostructures have the potential to make a larger impact on many industries.

LCC	Materials	Production	Use	Disposal
Materials	Carbon Nanostructures	Chemical Vapor deposition, other	Biomedical, Electrical, nuclear	Free existing, will be in cycle of nature
Energy	Energy Efficient		Energy Transport	
Chemistry	Carbon Allotrope			
Other				

Table 1 Generic LCC Table